

OPINION

Vaccine Protection Efficiency Compared with the Smart Application of Common-Sense Pandemic Control Measures

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ABSTRACT

Most recent NIH studies and CDC publication were able to estimate the vaccine efficacy variation overtime, and to remove the previous veil of ultimate and absolute protection against SARS-CoV-2, known as COVID-19 with respect to delta variant, propagated in the USA. The statistical data shows clear that Vaccines as Pfizer ad Moderna works, in spite their efficacies are decreasing with about 5%/month, are still able to protect in a more complex manner than masks and nano-engineered aerodynamics based protection measures. If these measures are referring to preventing inhalation of any hazardous material, no matter the type of viruses, the vaccine is dealing with the effects of virus inside the body after the intake took place. These vaccines were considered an ultimate protection and praised as such, as being in fact big pharma business, easy to be understood by masses with a real nature hazard mitigation IQ level much lower than the one made at national level based on the actual IQ tests customized to keep happy Caucasians, but fit well on Pacific Rim Asians. The problem with engineered protection is that one needs a smart population, cooperating synergistically, and be knowledgeable on when and how to use the protection in order to stop pandemic, insulate aggressor virus, create a vaccine and terminate the hazard. The current US practice is dominated by high-level mis-information and politicization of pandemic, where the actual spike in delta variant is due to CDC suppression of masks, without reaching a heard immunity, praising and enforcing vaccination aggravated by the incompetence of conservatives, who do not understand that a sick or dead person cannot enjoy constitutional freedoms, and do not distinguish between a life threat and a right, simply opposing to government without coming with alternate measures, having a disastrous effect on US population which with only 4% of world's population delivered more than 25% of world's casualties. The current milestone of 610,000 deaths and 40 million infected made the world leery about US exceptionalism and its planetary leadership.

INTRODUCTION

The actual 4th COVID-19 tsunami wave was launched by May by CDC incompetent suppression of protection measures as masks and social distancing based on myth of vaccine ultimate protection and children immunity to virus, which both turned out to be falsehoods at a high cost, steering political debates based on alternate realities.

As one may see in figure 1 in NY State, USA the infection rate in May-July was of 6.7%, meaning that 2 in 31 people got infected, and from these 2 in 29 were hospitalized, and further 1 in 6 died of COVID-19 [1]. The infection rate is variable and depends of the density of contagious subjects and rate of exposure of population and is about the same for the case of using vaccines versus the case of using engineered protective systems, and for the NY case is seen on the left side of (Figure 1). Using further CDC data, was possible to calculate vaccine efficacy [2]. It

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Figure 1 Vaccine protection effectiveness calculated in September 2021.

is seen on the right side, that environment general default protection factor is about -11.7 dB, which looks more like a “Russian Roulette” with a 16 cartridges magazine and 1 load, than being a real protection, saying that in about 16 exposures one gets sick. Ow in the case of fully vaccinated people only 1 in 12 will be detected as sick and reported. This is a vaccine protection factor of about -11.2 dB, almost equivalent with an N95 [3,4].

As one can see in (Figure 2) the engineered solutions deliver protection factors higher than the vaccine, but as results from figure 1 vaccine action is inside the contaminated body, while protective systems act outside preventing the body from being contaminated by killing and/or stopping the dangerous agents. In fact the infection rate is the same for vaccinated and unvaccinated subjects, but vaccine as a pharmaceutical compound acts inside the body inoculating successfully the virus evolution in 12 out of 13 cases that are not reported “sick”. More it continues its action and 11 out of 12 subjects recover without needing a hospitalization, while only 8% are hospitalized and from this only 9% of the hospitalized patients end up with death. The total death probability interpreted as a protection factor for vaccination reaches -31dB, that is low compared with what engineered aerodynamic photonic system may deliver as shown in figure 2 but requires a smart, educated population able to use the systems on the right time for the right duration [5]. Compared to these methods, vaccines are simple to administrate to population on the aspect of the subject has only to sit to be poked in the arm, without having any knowledge on the threat and protection mechanisms, while

is a centralized production, convenient for the state actors to control, distribute and collect the economic benefits. They also might not be so good and efficient because they need to leave room for the virus to multiply and mutate, as COVID-19 μ did recently, evading the actual vaccines very efficient for COVID-19 α , but sloppy on the last mutant, requiring the pharmaceutical companies produce an update, called booster, better tuned on the novel mutants and by this continuous action they manage to prevent NYSE actions from plummeting. More due to internal mechanisms inside immunity system the efficacy of vaccination is decreasing with time at a rate of 5%/month, making necessary a booster in about a year [6]. The engineered systems presented in figure 2 assure protection delivered by independent systems with a very slim probability for simultaneous failure, acting together and delivering a holistic protection against any aerosolized virus or bacteria. In the left side, at “B” one may see the collective protection factor delivered by masks acting as mouth jets stopper, while individual protection is delivered by masks acting as particulate and effluents filter, “C”. If a contagious person exhales inside a building that building has to deal with virioli, and those systems are presents at “A”, and “D”. Working together those engineered systems may deliver protection factors with orders of magnitude higher than the vaccines, but knowledge of application and discipline in spite being known for 100 years are difficult to implement on an under-educated, arrogant population. It was also noticed that after May 2021 CDC mask misinformation and relaxation, other viruses as Influenza, Coughing flu, ordinary colds, Krupp propagated successfully. The protection factor delivered by vaccination

Figure 2 Complex engineered protection against aerosolized virioli transmission.

is good enough, and if smartly applied together with engineered protective systems will drive to the best results, pandemic suppression in few weeks. Actual vaccination enforcements, without being sustained by an education and law application campaign, to prove as false, contradict and sanction misinformation triggering death and injury spread on social and mass media is counterproductive, as drives the misinformed people to double down in their misconceptions and only virus inflicted pain may be able to turn them smarter, but at a much higher cost for them and for the nation. One has also to consider the effect on physiologic enhancements brought to auto-immune system by the application of alimentary supplements that are quasi-pharmaceutical, still unregulated products, where the application has to be performed based on extensive details and naturist products knowledge.

CONCLUSION

In spite engineered protection systems are more effective and healthy in protection against aerosolized virioli transmission, the world prefers vaccination as ultimate protection, because it has minimal requirements at the user level, and it is concentrated in few high technology pharmaceutical companies, able to have an organized and efficient lobby on politicians to promote the products being also easy to understood and apply by medical staff. The

future belongs to these companies that permanently will have to upgrade the vaccines, keeping pace to new viruses mutants, that are here to stay.

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